

DEVELOPING CREATIVE ABILITY: A PRIORITY TASK OF MODERN EDUCATION

Kh.Kh. Khaydarov

Lecturer, Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences, Uzbekistan State Institute of Arts
and Culture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14992732>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of forming and developing creativity and creative abilities of the younger generation in educational institutions. The essence of the concept of creativity, its personal and cognitive components, approaches based on modern research, as well as the psychological and pedagogical foundations of forming a creative personality are highlighted. The importance of using innovative technologies and creative approaches in the educational process for developing creativity, conditions conducive to the development of creative abilities, and the prospects of using heuristic methods and game technologies in the pedagogical process are discussed. The development of creative abilities of the individual, continuous improvement of the content and methods of education are shown as an important factor in meeting the needs of society.*

Keywords: *creativity, creative ability, creativity, productive, intellectual approach, personal approach, synthetic approach, creative personality, traits of a creative personality, factors developing creativity.*

One of the most important goals of modern education is to educate young people in educational institutions who form an interest and need to assimilate national and universal values, are adaptable to rapidly developing and changing living conditions, are creatively active and enterprising, can independently determine the direction of their professional activity, can make independent decisions and are responsible for their actions. This process is aimed at ensuring the scientific, creative, and moral development of young people, forming active and responsible individuals who benefit society. Today, in light of the modern demands and needs of society, as well as the priority tasks of preparing a comprehensively mature and harmonious generation in educational institutions, educating a creative and creative personality remains one of the priority tasks.

In the context of continuous education, it is necessary to clarify the description of the concept of "creativity" in order to develop the theory and practice of forming and developing students' creative abilities, as well as innovative approaches to organizing educational processes.

In modern research, creativity (from Latin creatio - to create) is assessed as a multidimensional (personal, social) phenomenon dependent on intellectual and other factors.

Currently, various approaches are being studied in pedagogical and psychological research on the problem of creativity. In particular, approaches such as D.B.Bogoyavlenskaya's manifestation of intellectual initiative [1,138]; I.P.Koloshina's special structure of activity [2,64]; A.M.Matyushkin's holistic structure of the creative process [3,43]; A.Ya.Ponomarev's concept of developing internal plans of action [4,21] are among them. These approaches create favorable conditions for integrating ideas into a specific technology.

In the last decade, a number of pedagogical and psychological studies have been carried out on this issue. Some of them are devoted to the theory and practice of developing the creative potential of a teacher, the relationship between creativity and anxiety, the professional creativity of innovation management personnel, and the pedagogical aspects of personal development as a creator.

There are different approaches to defining the essence of creativity.

1. A.Tannenbaum, A.Oloh, D.B.Bogoyavlenskaya, A.Maslow - there are no separate creative abilities. Intellectual ability manifests itself as a necessity, but the conditions for personal creative activity are not sufficient. Motives, values, and special characteristics play a key role in the determination of creative behavior.

2. D.Guilford, K.Taylor, G.Gruber, Ya.A.Ponomarev - creative ability (creativity) is an independent factor not related to intelligence. There are slight differences between the level of intelligence and the level of creativity.

3. D.Wechsler, R.Weisberg, G.Eysenck, L.Terman, R.Sternberg - a high level of intelligence means a high level of creativity, and vice versa. There is no creative process as a specific form of psychological activity.

E.Fromm states that "creativity is wonder, the ability to find solutions in non-standard situations, the desire for novelty, and a deep understanding of personal experience" [5,204].

F.Barron considers the process of imagination and symbolization as the main factor of the creativity criterion, "internal activity that suddenly arises and continues during the person's activity" as a sign of creativity, and emphasizes that the absence of a result does not mean the absence of creativity [6,87].

One of the foundations for the emergence of the concept of creativity was the "investment theory" proposed by R.Sternberg. He considered creative people to be "those who buy an idea cheaply and sell it dearly" [7,16].

Currently, approaches to studying creativity based on cognitive or personal components can be described as follows.

1. **Productive, intellectual approach** (G.Ya.Eysenck, D.Wechsler, L.S.Leytes, L.Terman, J.Piaget, R.Sternberg, M.A.Kholodnaya). Creativity is assessed as a special random state of the subject's relatively general activity, readiness to go beyond the established boundaries to get out of an unknown situation when necessary, the ability to modify (adapt) ways to adapt to unknown situations.

2. **Personal approach** (F.Barron, D.B.Ermolaeva-Tomina, V.N.Kozlenko, A.Maslow, K.Rogers, E.Fromm). Creativity is the self-expression of a person, which means that creativity is a personal productive quality. Representatives of this approach believe that a person has certain characteristics that cause creativity, regardless of the level of intellectual development. They highlight the following directions of studying creative individuals: studying personal qualities and motives, studying the "Self" of a person related to creativity, studying the psychological characteristics of a person's creativity [8,103].

3. **Synthetic approach** (D.B.Bogoyavlenskaya, V.N.Druzhinin, S.Kaplin, A.M.Matyushkin, Ya.L.Ponomarev, D.Renzulli, A.Tannenbaum, D.Feldhusen, K.Heller). Creativity is a personal-cognitive style with two different natures. Initially developing as a purely cognitive education, creativity is strengthened in a motivational environment by forming cognitive

aspirations and goals. Under the influence of motivational factors, creative qualities are formed that ensure the use of creativity at the cognitive level.

The Swiss psychologist K.Jung emphasizes that while ordinary people carefully approach their feelings and tend to restrain them, a creative person, on the contrary, is not afraid to openly express the opposite characteristics of their nature [9,102].

According to the research of G.S.Altshuller, F.Barron, L.B.Ermolaeva-Tomina, V.N.Kozlenko, M.R.Ginzburg, K.Rogers, the following traits of a creative person can be highlighted:

1. **Openness to experience.** This means giving up stereotypes in situations created by someone or the public.
2. **Confidence in the unconscious.** The unconscious generates unconventional ideas, and the measure of talent is how successfully the consciousness can perceive and edit (translate into the language of logical thinking) ideas from the unconscious.
3. **The priority of the activity process over its result.** Enjoying the activity process is more enjoyable than aiming for a result. Aiming for a result causes depression in case of failure. Enjoying the process is a more valuable phenomenon and can directly lead to results.
4. **Experiencing emotions of maximum intensity.** The creative process takes place in the context of bright and completely opposite emotions: from the joy of invention to the depression of helplessness, from uplifted inspiration to spiritual depression.
5. **Uniqueness of self-expression.** This quality of a person can manifest itself in showing their individuality (ingenuity, eloquence, manner of self-expression, individual habits, etc.) or in showing themselves as a socially successful person.
6. **Desire to focus on current activity.** A creative person strives to fully realize their talent and does everything in their power to develop the talents of those around them so that they can have partners in society.
7. **Purposeful creation of creativity.** Many creative people strive to solve some general problems while solving specific tasks.

It is worth noting that many foreign studies devoted to the study of creativity have been conducted in connection with the psychology of creativity and the assessment of a person's creative potential. The results obtained in this area are still used today.

The word "creativity" etymologically means "to create" in Latin. In English, two forms of creativity are used with different meanings:

- creativity - essentially means creation;
- creative activity or creative work - essentially creative process.

In Uzbek, both interpretations mean creativity. Their differentiation is used when additional concepts are needed - activity, process, etc.

Creativity should be interpreted not as some signs of creative talent or similar aspects, but as creative talent.

According to M.A.Kholodnaya's definition, creativity is the creation of many diverse and original ideas as a result of activity carried out in an unlimited environment [10,33].

Creativity is an important component of general ability. Creativity means implementing novelty in practice, understanding problems and contradictions, and abandoning stereotypical ideas. Creativity manifests itself in the speed of processes of combining new ideas into a general state, creating ideas of extraordinarily unique content, and seeing complex aspects in simple things.

The problem of forming and developing a creative personality, its activity has a very rich history. In the 20-30s of the XX century, such pedagogues as P.P.Blonsky, S.T.Shatsky, B.L.Yavorsky, B.V.Asafiev, N.Ya.Biryusova made a significant contribution to researching solutions to the pedagogical problem of forming and developing a creative personality.

The well-known psychologist L.S.Rubinshtein expresses the following idea about the possibility of developing a person's creative abilities through purposeful engagement: "people's talents are not only manifested, but also formed during their activities" [11,25].

In the education of creativity, hereditary factors also determine the levels of a person's creativity. However, a favorable environment is also necessary to realize talent.

Also, the needs of society determine such things as understanding the importance of creative activity, personal motives and emotions, acquired knowledge, and the ability to use them to create something new. They are distinguished by their uniqueness, originality, and socio-historical uniqueness.

Creative activity, as the basis for personal development, has a certain structure and content. Although the main element of the structure of creative activity is the goal of the activity, it, of course, undergoes transformation in accordance with the interests and internal motives that arise in the student during the educational process. Their compliance with the goals of the activity is the beginning of the student's creative development. Enriching the student's knowledge and mastering experiences perfect the content of creative activity. From a psychological point of view, a person's creative activity requires the harmonious work of memory, perception, sensation, attention, thinking, and reasoning.

In our opinion, one of the main socio-pedagogical conditions for developing creativity in students is the use of innovative technologies, creativity development programs, and methods in organizing their educational activities. Research devoted to solving this problem is being carried out in various directions, one of which is the use of active and heuristic methods in the pedagogical process. Also, game methods and methods of solving creative and heuristic problems can be recognized as one of the promising directions in developing creativity in students.

Thus, as a number of researchers have emphasized, the following factors determine the development of creativity and the activation of creative potential:

- Considering the search for new effective ways and methods aimed at developing and activating the creative abilities of the individual;
- Humanizing educational institutions in connection with recognizing the rights and freedoms of the student, creating conditions for realizing their professional interests, identifying and developing creative abilities, and mastering universal and professional culture;
- A creative person manifests and develops in an educational institution in a favorable psychological environment, where educational activities are aimed at professional and creative activity, and educational activities are aimed at developing students' creative thinking;
- The process of developing students' creative abilities requires the continuous development of the content, forms, and methods of education, creating a creativity environment, and directing the scientific and pedagogical activities of the educational institution to the independent development of students' creative abilities.

Developing the creative abilities of the individual is one of the most important indicators of the development of society. One of the main requirements of modern approaches used in

educational processes in educational institutions is the development of students' creative activity abilities. This, in turn, must be carried out in connection with the needs of society.

REFERENCES

1. Богоявленская Д.Б. Психология творческих способностей: учебное пособие. М.: Академия, 2002. 320 с.
2. Калошина И.П. Психология творческой деятельности: учебное пособие для студентов вузов /. - М.: ЮНИТИ, 2003. 430 с.
3. Матюшкин А.М. Развитие творческой активности школьников. М.: Педагогика, 1991. 155 с.
4. Пономарев Й.А. Исследование проблем психологии творчества. Сборник статей. М., Наука, 1983. 132 с.
5. Психология: Словарь/Под общ. ред. А.В Петровского, М.Г.Ярошевского. – 2-е изд., испр. и доп. – М.: Политиздан, 1990. – С.393.
6. Barron F. Puttins creativity to work // Sternberg R.,Tardif T. (eds). The nature of creativity. – Cambridge Cambr. Press, 1988/ - P/ 76-98
7. Sternberg R. General intellectual ability //Human abilities by R. Sternberg. 1985. P. 5-31.
8. Дорфман Л.Я., Ковалева Г.В. //Основные направления исследований креативности в науке и искусстве Вопросы психологии. – 1999. - №2. – С.101 – 105.
9. Г.В.Ковалева //Вопросы психологии. – 1999. - №2. – С.101 – 105.
10. Холодная М. А. Перспективы исследований в области психологии способностей // Психологический журнал. 2007. № 1. С. 28–37.
11. Рубинштейн Л.С. Проблемы общей психологии. – М.: Педагогика, 1973. – С. 43.